

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.514 Max: 62.756	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1410 ☒ Natural ☐ Anthropic	
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In cross-section? ☐ Yes ☒ No	In elevation drawing? ☐ Yes ☒ No	Photos: ☒ Yes ☐ No #: 2188-2190	Photo Model: ☐ Yes ☒ No #:
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DEFINITION SOIL AND BIG SLAB IN COURTYARD	Covered by ☒ SU: 1384	Fills ☒ SU: 1229	Filed by ☐ SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? ☐ Color ☒ Composition ☐ Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS ☐ Accumulation ☐ Construction ☐ Cutting ☐ Erosion ☒ Collapse ☐ Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay 50% silt 47% sand 3%
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☒ Cohesive
☒ Pottery ☐ Nails ☐ Tiles ☐ Marble ☐ Amphorae ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Dolia ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Mosaic tiles ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Mortar ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Coins ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Other (specify) ☐ Glass	☒ Tufo (specify) 1 block ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)	Compaction ☒ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft
			Color ☐ Black ☒ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: ☒ Original ☐ Not Original
Northern Limit	☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1384, 1477	Covers: 1230
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1229

OBSERVATIONS
dry, sunny conditions, good visibility.

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: situated at the western edge of trench B, near threshold SU 1384 and close to sewer SU's 1228/1230
Shape: ashlar block, 1 single ashlar block, very big, with soil stuck to it

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Big ashlar, probably originally built into the retaining wall of the house (SU 1245) and then, during the renewal of the floor surface or during the construction of the drainage channel SU 1228, it was redeposited where we found it some 2000 years later.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by

SAL

on

19/7/2011

Revised by

AMH

on

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PDF'd by

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on

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on

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